

SYNERGISTIC ROLE OF SELECTIVE HERBAL COMBINATIONS WITH ALLOPATHIC DRUGS AMONG PATIENTS OF CHRONIC DISEASES AND WAY FORWARD FOR COVID-19 PATIENTS

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ABSTRACT

Herbal preparations in combination of allopathic drugs recommended by physicians were found highly effective to patients sufferings from diabetes, heart disease, asthma and joint pain. The application of okhra mucilage results instant relief on skin burn encountered in day to day work in the Indian kitchen

Key Words: Allopathic drugs, herbal treatment, synergistic effect, diabetes, hyperlipidaemia, creatinine, uric acid, hypertension, asthma, joint pain, burn

By trial and error method, man learned herbs use for curing various diseases. Such age old practice paved way for the discovery of the most modern effective drugs of today from herbs such as aspirin from willow bark, digoxin from foxglove, quinine from cinchona bark and morphine from the opium poppy) (Vickers and Zollman 1999).

The medieval history is full of records of medicine men/healers relying on herbs for curing various ailments. This practice has continued even today in the developing and underdeveloped countries where more than 75-80% populations rely on vicinal herbs. The onset of industrial revolution in the 19th century paved was for a new discipline “Allopathy” for disease cure; a term coined in 1810 by Samuel Hahnemann (1755-1843). Because of rapid scientific advances, and cheaper and faster cure of various ailments, allopathy became most popular in the healthcare system globally particularly in the developed world. People’s experience of drug reactions and other side effects during allopathic treatments in the 1960s drew their attentions to relatively safe age old practice of herbal products. World Health Organization also recommended use of traditional plant based medicines in healthcare in the developing countries (Winslow and Kroll 1998).

The development of tools and techniques has led to isolation of active ingredients (chemicals) from medicinal plants that followed validation of their claimed role in the animal models. Several plant species have been found effective in the treatment of even the most dreadful diseases such as AIDS,

Herpes, H1N1 and even SARS-CoV. Being a botanist and eco-toxicologist, I have been using various medicinal herbs for treating various ailments in my family for a long time. This interest grew further after superannuation (year 2015) that led in depth studies of various research articles published in peer reviewed journals on rejuvenating role of medicinal herbs (especially those growing in Rajasthan) in the disease induced animal models. Only those herbs found highly effective in ameliorating role were picked collected from wild, sun/shade dried and powdered. The powdered preparations of few plant species were also purchased from standard Pharma companies. Interestingly all of them are extensively used in various Ayurvedic preparations since ages and the only difference was combinations of herbs used here.

My family members (especially myself, wife, elder sisters) having faith on earlier recommendations for curing common diseases volunteered for herbal preparations for diabetes, asthma, joint pain, poor immunity, hyperlipidaemia, high uric acid, renal disorder etc. We shared benefits of herbal treatment with our close friends and they joined us. I was in constant touch with everyone though email (by questionnaire), phone and what’s app messages taking feedback about health problems persisting before and after herbal treatment in combination with allopathic drugs recommended by the qualified Doctors for the aforesaid diseases. Emails and what’s app messages are available with me to verify claims made herein for synergistic role of herbs with allopathic drugs. This publication includes success stories of persons suffering from aforesaid diseases.

Diabetes

The numbers of diabetes patients (Type-2) are staggering globally especially in India because of sedentary life style and poor food habits. This incurable disease is affecting 8.8% adult population as per International Diabetes Federation. The decoction was prepared adding one tablespoon of herbal mixture in 1L of potable water in a steel pressure cooker in the night (half a tablespoon for 500L). The gas was turned off after one whistle and decoction filtered in the morning (almost after 8h) was stored in the refrigerator and has been referred to as Type “A” hereafter in the text. Friends and relatives suffering from diabetes volunteered for trial of herbal treatment. They provided data about allopathic medicines and sugar fasting from time to time by emails and What’s app.

Patients on allopathic medicines: These patients were using various medicines such as glimiperide, metformin etc. for controlling diabetes. They were orally administered lukewarm decoction (250mL) in the morning (before meal) for one week and then for 3days in a week. A gap of 15days followed after every two month of herbal treatment (though allopathic drug/s continued) for volunteer/s below 60years. Their diets remained as before herbal intake.

Case 1: Sex: Male; Age: 75yr., Diabetic: >5years; Locality = Jaipur; Metformin (1000mg-Morning & 500mg-Evening), also complaints of high blood pressure & constipation. Fasting was higher (170-150; Oct. 2019) before herbal treatment (**Type -A**). Herbal treatment was started in the first week of Nov. 2019. Followings are the sugar fasting readings taken at fortnight intervals of herbal treatment.

138, 154, 157, 150, 121, 133, 114 (3rd April 2020), 109 (20th April 2020) and 110 (27th April 2020).

Besides reduction in dose of allopathic drug (500mg-Morning & 500mg-Evening) and sugar level (well below WHO limit); other benefits were sound sleep and relief in constipation.

Case 2: Sex: Female; Age: 70yr., Diabetic: >5years; Locality = Jaipur; Metformin (1000mg-Morning & 500mg-Evening), Fasting found higher (170-200; Oct. 2019) before herbal treatment declined gradually after combined treatment (**Type -A + Drug**) in the first week of Nov. 2019. Followings are the sugar fasting readings taken at fortnight intervals.

149, 158, 171, 147, 166, 185, 145 (3rd April 2020), 136(3rd April 2020), 123 (3rd April 2020).

The benefits include reduction in the dose of allopathic drug and sugar level (well below WHO limit).

Case 3: Sex: Female; Age: 65yr., Diabetic: 6years; Locality = Jaipur; Glimiperide + Metamorphin (500mg) before lunch; Fasting was little higher (135-145; year 2013; HBA1C = 6.8) than normal limit and blood pressure also; 90-100 (diastolic)- 140-150 (systolic); Highly sensitive to cold and cough to be cured only after 5days allopathic treatment. Food habits: Potato & rice minimum 2-3days in a week. Patient has family history of diabetes. Her father was on insulin for almost 10years.

Herbal treatment (**Type -A**) was started in the year 2018 (rainy season). HBA1C data ranged between 6.0-6.5 (March 2020); Drug: Ziten – M (1/day); other benefits were reduction in blood pressure (65-70-diastolic; 110-120-systolic) and joint pain. Develop resistance to cold and cough cured within 3 days even without allopathic treatment suggesting immunomodulatory role of “A”.

Case 4: Sex: Female; Age: 60yr., Diabetic: 10years; Locality = Jaipur. She is a breast cancer (operated & cured) patient suffering from Type-2 diabetes possibly as a side effect of chemotherapy. Allopathic medicine/s: Fasting 130-145, pp. 170 -200, Medicine: gluconorm G1 and g2forte.

Herbal treatment (**Type -A**) began in May 2019. Sugar fasting data is tabulated below.

Date	Fasting	PP
30/05/19	121	Not Checked
16/07/19	158	258
24/07/19	142	Not Checked
2/8/2019	148	Not Checked
28/08/19	155	Not Checked
30/11/19	133	165
1/12/2019	113	Not Checked
2/12/2019	112	Not Checked
4/12/2019	123	130
7/12/2019	108	Not Checked
8/12/2019	112	

Herbal treatment was discontinued after March 2020. Presently sugar fasting and pp continued to be low (13th May 2020) sugar fasting: 97-110; PP: 135-150; Medicines: gluconorm G1 and G2 forte (same as before herbal treatment).

Case 5: Sex: Male; Age: 55yr., fasting: 150-153; Drug: Glador M2/day; Herbal treatment (**Type -A**) began in Feb. 2020. Sugar fasting data (113,100, 114) is for March and April 2020. Patient followed no diet consuming potato and rice prior to diabetes detection.

Case 6: Sex: Female; Age: 54yr., Diabetic: >5years; Locality = Varanasi; Sugar fasting after allopathic medicine (detail not provided): 300-350; also complain severe joint pain.

Herbal treatment started in November 2018 was discontinued after 3 months. It was restarted again in Nov. 2019 and continued (4th May 2020). Sugar fasting ranged = 180-190. There is great relief in joint pain.

Insulin Patients: These were using insulin (18-30units) 2-3 times in a day alongwith other supporting drugs. These were given 250mL of decoction (Type-A) initially in both morning and evening and after wards only in the morning/day. Case studies of three patients (name undisclosed) are described below.

Case 1. Sex: Male; Age: 54yr. Locality = Jaipur; Insulin dose (before A): Lantus 30units (Morning & Evening), also complains neuropathy such as burning sensation in feet & constipation. Fasting – 170 (20th Jan. 2020).

21st Jan. 2020: 30unit Lantus + decoction (250mL morning & evening); Fasting: 127

22 Jan.-31st Jan. 2020: 20 unit Lantus + decoction (250mL morning & evening)

26Jan. 2020: Fasting: 167

28th Jan.: Fasting: 150

30th Jan.: Fasting: 125

31st Jan.: Fasting: 140

Also reported little relief in neuropathy (but not in constipation). Unfortunate he discontinued after 10days of herbal treatment.

Case 2: Sex: Male; Age: 44yr. Locality = Vizag, Andhra Pradesh; Habit: Crazy for sweets; Insulin dose (before A): Lantus 30units (3times/day), Fasting – 404 (30th Aug. 2019). Sugar fasting after Type- A + drug treatment were as follow.

5th Sept. = 243

11Sept. =299

14th Sept. = 270

19th Sept. = 254

22nd Sept. = 209

26th Sept. = 186

4th Oct. = 162

12th Oct. = 170

15th Oct. = 156

21st Oct. = 140

29th Nov. = 243 (stop decoction due to out of station business tours in the beginning of Nov. 2019).

Case study 3: Sex: Male; Age: 60yr. Locality = Jaipur; Diabetic patient for more than 10years; Fasting = 150-170 (April 2019), **Glargin** insulin dose since June 2018: 18 units (3 times /day) + Instamet 50/1000 + G1 + Night Injection;

After start of decoction (Type –A) in May 2019 + allopathic drugs; Insulin 18 units (3 times /day) + Instamet 50/1000 + G1 + Night Injection; Data of fasting and PP are presented below.

The drugs doses were reduced gradually by the physician and findings are as follow.

Date	Fasting	PP
30/05/19	131	Not Checked
2/8/2019	123	Not Checked
7/8/2019	170	Not Checked
10/8/2019	137	Not Checked
14/8/19	132	Not Checked
22/8/19	128	Not Checked
28/8/19	142	Not Checked
30/11/19	97	154
1/12/2019	90	Not Checked
2/12/2019	92	Not Checked
4/12/2019	85	145
5/12/2019	83	136
6/12/2019	Not Checked	132
7/12/2019	Not Checked	170

The drugs doses were reduced gradually by the physician and findings are as follow.

Date	Fasting	PP	Regular Insulin			Glargin Insulin	Herbal Medicine		Allopathic		Remarks
			Insulin Dose			Before Sleep	Morning	Evening	Before Break fast	Before Dinner fast	
			Before Break fast	Before Lunch	Before Dinner						
April Month	172	245-265	14 unit	14 unit	14 unit	16 unit	Nil	NIL	Instamet 50/1000	G1	
30/05/19	176	Not Checked	14 unit	14 unit	14 unit	14 unit	Y	Y	Instamet 50/1000	G1	
2/8/2019	178	Not Checked	14 unit	14 unit	14 unit	14 unit	Y	Y	Instamet 50/1000	G1	
7/8/2019	170	Not Checked	14 unit	14 unit	14 unit	14 unit	Y	Y	Instamet 50/1000	G1	
10/8/2019	137	Not Checked	12 unit	12 unit	12 unit	14 unit	Y	Y	Instamet 50/1000	G1	
14/8/19	132	Not Checked	12 unit	12 unit	12 unit	14 unit	Y	Y	Instamet 50/1000	G1	
22/8/19	128	Not Checked	12 unit	12 unit	12 unit	14 unit	Y	Y	Instamet 50/1000	G1	
28/8/19	142	Not Checked	12 unit	12 unit	12 unit	14 unit	Y	Y	Instamet 50/1000	G1	
30/11/19	97	154	12 unit	12 unit	12 unit	14 unit	Y	Y	Instamet 50/1000	G1	
1/12/2019	90	Not Checked	12 unit	12 unit	12 unit	14 unit	Y	Y	Instamet 50/1000	G1	
2/12/2019	92	Not Checked	8 unit	8 unit	8 unit	14 unit	Y	Y	Instamet 50/1000	G1	
4/12/2019	85	145	8 unit	8 unit	8 unit	14 unit	Y	Y	Instamet 50/1000	G1	
5/12/2019	83	136	8 unit	8 unit	8 unit	14 unit	Y	Y	Instamet 50/1000	G1	
6/12/2019	Not Checked	132	8 unit	8 unit	8 unit	14 unit	Y	Y	Instamet 50/1000	G1	
7/12/2019	Not Checked	170	8 unit	8 unit	8 unit	14 unit	Y	Y	Instamet 50/1000	G1	
8/12/2019	Not Checked	Not Checked	8 unit	8 unit	8 unit	14 unit	Y	Y	Instamet 50/1000	G1	
11/12/2019	96	Not Checked	8 unit	8 unit	8 unit	14 unit	Y	Y	Instamet 50/1000	G1	
13/12/2019	Not Checked	146	8 unit	8 unit	8 unit	14 unit	Y	Y	Instamet 50/1000	G1	
14/12/2019	101	178	8 unit	8 unit	8 unit	14 unit	Y	Y	Instamet 50/1000	G1	
18/12/2019	105	165	8 unit	8 unit	8 unit	14 unit	Y	Y	Instamet 50/1000	G1	
25/12/2019	97	156	8 unit	8 unit	8 unit	14 unit	Y	Y	Instamet 50/1000	G1	
27/12/2019	103	162	8 unit	8 unit	8 unit	14 unit	Y	Y	Instamet 50/1000	G1	
3/1/2020	121	173	8 unit	8 unit	8 unit	14 unit	Y	Y	Instamet 50/1000	G1	
7/1/2020	101	163	8 unit	8 unit	8 unit	14 unit	Y	Y	Instamet 50/1000	G1	
11/1/2020	95	143	6 unit	6 unit	6 unit	14 unit	Y	Y	Instamet 50/1000	G1	
21/01/2020	99	147	6 unit	6 unit	6 unit	14 unit	Y	Y	Instamet 50/1000	G1	

26/01/2020	95	139	6 unit	6 unit	6 unit	14 unit	Y	Y	Instamet 50/1000	G1	
29/01/2021	99	137	6 unit	6 unit	6 unit	14 unit	Y	Y	Instamet 50/1000	G1	
30/01/2022	90	141	6 unit	6 unit	6 unit	14 unit	Y	Y	Instamet 50/1000	G1	
31/01/2023	93	144	6 unit	6 unit	6 unit	14 unit	Y	Y	Instamet 50/1000	G1	
4/2/2020	101	151	4 unit	4 unit	4 unit	14 unit	Y	Y	Instamet 50/1000	G1	
9/2/2020	108	149	4 unit	4 unit	4 unit	14 unit	Only One Time		Instamet 50/1000	G1	
17/02/2020	102	148	4 unit	4 unit	4 unit	14 unit	Only One Time		Instamet 50/1000	G1	
25/02/2020	99	143	4 unit	4 unit	4 unit	14 unit	Only One Time		Instamet 50/1000	G1	
1/3/2020	113	152	4 unit	4 unit	4 unit	14 unit	Only One Time		Instamet 50/1000	G1	
7/3/2020	101	143	4 unit	4 unit	4 unit	14 unit	Only One Time		Instamet 50/1000	G1	
11/3/2020	99	135	4 unit	4 unit	4 unit	14 unit	Only One Time		Instamet 50/1000	G1	
17/03/2020	95	138	4 unit	4 unit	4 unit	14 unit	NOT Taken Since Last one week		Instamet 50/1000	G2	Allopathic Medicine G1 replaced by G2
21/03/2020	85	Not Checked	4 unit	4 unit	4 unit	14 unit	NOT Taken		Instamet 50/1000	G2	G2 Regular Low diabetes
23/03/2020	87	Not Checked	4 unit	4 unit	4 unit	14 unit	NOT Taken		Instamet 50/1000	G2	G2 Regular Low diabetes
25/03/2020	75(Low)	Not Checked	4 unit	4 unit	4 unit	Stopped	NOT Taken		Instamet 50/1000	G2	Regular/Night Injection stopped G2
26/03/2020	101	142	4 unit	4 unit	4 unit	Stopped	NOT Taken		Instamet 50/1000	G2	Regular/Night Injection stopped G2
27/03/2020	108	144	4 unit	4 unit	4 unit	Stopped	NOT Taken		Instamet 50/1000	G2	Regular/Night Injection stopped G2
28/03/2020	105	154	4 unit	4 unit	4 unit	Stopped	NOT Taken		Instamet 50/1000	G2	Regular/Night Injection stopped G2
29/03/2020	99	156	4 unit	4 unit	4 unit	Stopped	NOT Taken		Instamet 50/1000	G2	Regular/Night Injection stopped G2
30/03/2020	101	143	4 unit	4 unit	4 unit	Stopped	NOT Taken		Instamet 50/1000	G2	Regular/Night Injection stopped G2
31/03/2020	105	161	4 unit	4 unit	4 unit	Stopped	NOT Taken		Instamet 50/1000	G2	Regular/Night Injection stopped

After continuation of herbal treatment withdrawal, its ameliorative role continued and important data are tabulated.

Date	Fasting	PP	Insulin	Instamet	G2	Cardex-5 mg	Remarks
2/5/2020	87	148	3 unit	3 unit	Instamet 50/1000	G2	Cardex-5 mg G2 Regular/Night Injection stopped
6/5/2020	95	158	3 unit	3 unit	Instamet 50/1000	G2	Cardex-5 mg G2 Regular/Night Injection stopped
9/5/2020	105	161	3 unit	3 unit	Instamet 50/1000	G2	Cardex-5 mg G2 Regular/Night Injection stopped
11/5/2020	99	144	3 unit	3 unit	Instamet 50/1000	G2	Cardex-5 mg G2 Regular/Night Injection stopped

It is evident that herbal treatment reduced insulin dose gradually, replaced G1 with G2 and stopped bed time injection. Furthermore, withdrawal of herbal treatment has no adverse effect. The patient is now consuming herbal formulation occasionally (1-2days) in a week.

It is evident from the ongoing account that all diabetic patients were having high sugar fasting due to resistant insulin in their blood which becomes effective after herbal treatment thereby reducing intake of injectable insulin and other drugs. This hypothesis still needs experimental validation. Besides herbal treatment has other benefits to the patients.

Heart Problem: Sex: Male; Age: 54yr. Locality = Indore; Disease = Clestrole (diagnosed by a heart specialist in Bombay Hospital in 2013), Medicines: Rosuvastatin-40mg, Plavix (Clopidogrel sulphate) and Telpres AM-40mg. Health problems persisting after allopathic medication- Dyspnea on exertion, high cholesterol, inflammation in whole body, constipation & gas problem, high blood pressure and also pulse rate.

Herbal treatment (Type-A) started in October 2019 (initially daily for two weeks and later 3days in week) improved lipid profile and reduced patient sufferings state earlier.

	Total cholesterol	LDL	HDL	Triglycerides
Before treatment	245	210	37	175
After 60days	178	44	116	90

Inflammation (whole body)

One patient (Female, age- 50yrs.) from Indore had a serious problem body inflammation was benefitted after consumption of herbal decoction (Type-A) for 3days/week. Other benefits were; relief in joint pain, digestion and blood pressure.

Asthma

One patient; Sex: Female; Age: 71yrs. Locality = Mathura; Chronic patient of asthma for more than 20years, Lungs: Partially shrink, highly sensitive cold even during summer; Allopathic Treatment: Nayati Multispecialty Hospital, Mathura for 4years till today. Moderate relief but often suffering from fever after minor exertion, problem becoming severe during winter and often admitted to ICU in 2018.

After herbal (Type -A)+ allopathic drugs: Feel much better though complaint of fever continued.

After herbal (Type -A; Morning)+ Type B (at bed time)+ allopathic drugs: Incidence of fever reduced to minimum, incidence of fever occasional and overall feel much better and cheerful.

Joint Pain

Joint pain mostly common among elderly peoples has been attributed to osteoarthritis, gout including inflammation of the cushioning pads around joints. Herbal decoction (Type -A) was also found highly effective in reducing joint pain possibly due to its anti-inflammatory activities (Category -1) but less effective to those having crystals of monosodium urate (formed due to high uric acid) in the joints and tendons (Category-2).

Ten peoples (age= 55-75yrs; 2 males and 8 females) of category -1 got relief when used herbal decoction 3days / week along with exercise. One of these sufferers having knee

replacement in the year 2016 had severe pain in the knees and also often muscle cramps in her legs.

The author suffered from knee ligament injuries in an accident in the year 1999 causing frequent knee lock condition and severe joint pain. He was diagnosed with high uric condition (>5years) (up to 10.5 mg/dL) in 2015 resulting swelling in feet, excessive itchiness in whole body, dry skin and urate crystals in the excretory system. Type-A decoction declined creatinine levels (1.2mg/dL to 0.7 mg/dL), blood pressure (Vintel CTC: 90-140; Type-A + Vintel CTC: 80 & 120-130) and improved immunity (no viral infection common during weather change since two years) but not uric acid. Sneezing due to cold at one occasion cured without medicine within 24h. The relief in joint pains was also not much. The herbal decoction became effective when consumed with another herbal preparation (Type-C) found highly effective for reducing uric acid level to normal range, clearing of urate crystals in the excretory system as revealed in Sonography including constipation. Now I walk comfortably though still face problem while going down on the slope and stairs. I did not take any allopathic drug for reducing uric acid levels in the blood and now consume pulses, green peas, tomato, spinach, cauliflower and dairy products banned earlier. Exercise has been found to have synergistic effect in relieving joint pains in all cases.

Burn

Due to careless attitude, burning of hands with stove in the kitchen is very common problem in the households. Being fond of cooking, I also encountered with this problem and accidentally discovered immediate relief when applied spilt

water soaked okra on the burn surface. To reaffirm this experience, intentionally burn my skin touching hot surface and experience similar relief at every occasion. It is likely that mucilage of okra has some medicinal properties but this needs further investigation.

It is evident Type-A was effective in all health problems becoming much more effective with Type-B for asthma and Type-C for joint pain due to high uric acid. **Detailed information of various herbs used has not been disclosed because of potential for patent applications.** Since COVID-19 patients suffering from these chronic diseases had higher mortality, therefore there is a possibility of **exploring ameliorating role of "Type A" formulation on the peoples (suffering from them) kept in isolation wards, particularly COVID warriors.**

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